

ICCOB OA 013

**Long Term with Dasatinib Therapy Among Imatinib-Intolerant Patients
with Chronic Phase Chronic Myeloid Leukemia: A Randomized Study**

Amit Kumar Dutta

Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi

Email: drakdutta81@gmail.com

Imatinib is the standard-of-care treatment for most chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) patients in chronic phase (CP). However, some patients suffer from low-grade side-effects that, in the long run, severely affect the quality of life and require treatment discontinuation due to toxicities. Analog of Imatinib Therapy, the second-generation tyrosine kinase inhibitor dasatinib, used as second-line treatment, has shown to be a valid option in patients with CP-CML after intolerance to prior Imatinib Therapy. Achieving early molecular response as a reduction in *BCR-ABL1* transcripts to $\leq 10\%$ at 6 months after initiating tyrosine kinase inhibitor treatment, has been shown to improve the probability of achieving a subsequent deep molecular response and to be associated with superior progression-free and overall survival in chronic myeloid leukemia in chronic phase (CML-CP). Treatment was well tolerated, and side-effects were mild. The results of this first prospective study support early monitoring of patients treated with first line imatinib, and suggest that switching to Dasatinib in cases of suboptimal response may offer clinical benefit. This finding, although limited to a small cohort of CP-CML patients, supports the view that a therapy switch from Imatinib to Dasatinib induces a reduction of symptom burden, improves patient compliance and shows clinical efficacy in achieving and sustaining deep molecular responses. Further Long-term follow-up is needed to assess the long-term clinical benefit of early switching.

Keywords: CML, BCR-ABL1, Imatinib, Tyrosine Kinase, Dasatinib; Second-line Treatment, Follow Up Study, Statistical Analysis